

GALLERY: Kildonan – Iron Age

From left to bottom right: woman weaving from Kildonan reconstruction; scan – excavation of Hut-Circles at Kiphedir, Kildonan; Stone Bowl – 3D; reconstruction of Kildonan landscape; construction of roundhouse from HeritageAtHome talk

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During the Iron Age the Strath of Kildonan in Sutherland was home to many small farming communities. The relatively mild climate of this period enabled the cultivation of barley, wheat, and oats, and the keeping of horses, sheep, and cattle. Although much of the land had been cleared for agriculture, areas of woodland survived (providing shelter for deer, wild boar, and wolves).

The Iron Age residents of Kildonan lived in circular roundhouses, made of stone and turf, with conical thatched roofs. Hut circles from these long-ago dwellings can still be seen today. More than 350 hut circles have been identified in Kildonan.

The roundhouses provided shelter for humans and animals. They were focused around a central hearth, with bays for sleeping and stalls for animals towards the walls of the house. Roundhouses

were common throughout the British Isles. However, many of the roundhouses in Kildonan have specific regional variations – including passageways in the walls.

Reconstructions

Kildonan – Iron Age Reconstruction [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4580364](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4580364)

Iron Age roundhouse in the Strath of Kildonan (Open Virtual Worlds)

There is a video preview of the reconstruction on [Vimeo](#).

A 360° tour can be found on [Roundme](#).

This reconstruction shows how roundhouses near Caen in the Strath of Kildonan may have looked about 2000 years ago. The dwellings are set within a wider landscape, which was already profoundly shaped by human activity. Partial deforestation, and the impact of growing crops and grazing animals, made this Iron Age environment far from its original wild state.

3D Objects

List of 3D objects from the Timespan Museum currently published on Zenodo.

Bone Spatula [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557531](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557531)

Bone Antler [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4570288](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4570288)

Spindle Worl 1 [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557481](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557481)

Spindle Worl 2 [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557442](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557442)

Stone Bowl [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557392](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557392)

Stone Crucible [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557512](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557512)

Stone Lamp [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4557495](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4557495)

Associated Resources

A tour of the reconstruction and discussion by Jacquie Aitken of the research behind it can be found [here](#). Find out about life in the Iron Age and the effects of changing climates on these farming communities and learn more about the processes involved in turning an archaeological site into a digital reconstruction. This event is part of **CINE: See the Past, Imagine the Future**.

How Has the Gallery Been Used?

The reconstruction was featured as part of a [virtual event](#) in collaboration with Timespan in June 2020. It is part of the wider [CINE](#) project which focuses on digitally representing heritage in northern environments.

When Was the Gallery Published?

This version of the reconstruction was released to the public in May 2020. The gallery was published May 2021.

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Discover More

Information held by Historic Environment Scotland about pre-historic sites in and around Caen can be accessed via [Canmore](#). CANMORE

You can see how the area near the Caen Burn looks today on [Google Maps](#).

Project Funding

This reconstruction was part of the [CINE](#) project for digital heritage in northern environments. The project received funding from the European Union's [Northern Periphery and Arctic Programme](#).

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